

CAN INTERNAL MARKETING HELP TO REDUCE PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS TEACHERS' TURNOVER INTENTION?

Muhammed Ömer Eren¹ⁱ,

Gökhan Dokuzoğlu²

¹Physical Education and Sports Teacher,
Balıkesir, Turkey

²Physical Education and Sports Teacher,
Aydın, Turkey

Abstract:

In this study, internal marketing and turnover intention were discussed, and the effect of internal marketing on physical education and sports teachers' turnover intentions. The internal marketing scale and the turnover intention scale, previously developed, were used as data collection tools. In the study, 201 physical education teachers participated. First reliability analysis and then descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analyses were performed on the obtained data. At the end of the study, it has been understood that internal marketing had an effect on turnover intention, in other words, internal marketing practices can help decrease teachers' turnover intentions.

Keywords: internal marketing, turnover intention, physical education and sports teacher

1. Introduction

It is becoming more and more important for organizations to make products with more equipped employees. Because one of the prerequisites for quality production is to have skilled employees (Tabancali and Krumaz, 2014). However, it is not enough to have only skilled employees. However, it is inevitable to make various practices that increase the motivation and satisfaction of the employees. If employees are not satisfied, their turnover intention will arise, and then they will quit (Abbas, Raja, Darr and Bouckennooghe, 2012). This interrupts the production process (Poddar and Madupalli, 2012). Internal marketing can be seen as an important factor in preventing turnover intention.

Internal marketing is the practice of motivating employees by meeting their needs (Rafiq and Ahmed, 2000). According to this approach, the customer is divided into two as "internal customer" and "external customer". While the internal customer constitutes

ⁱ Correspondence: momer54@hotmail.com

the employees of the whole company, the external customer is the people who receive service from the organization (Berry, 1995). Internal marketing suggests that internal customers (employees) should be satisfied first as a prerequisite for the formation of external customer satisfaction (Berry and Parasuraman, 1991). Satisfied employee deals better with external customers, thus increasing the satisfaction of the external customer (Ahmed and Rafiq, 2003). Satisfied external customers also benefit more from the organization, thereby increasing the organization's performance (Koys, 2001).

The turnover intention is that an employee experiences feelings of leaving their organization (Mahdi et al., 2012). There are many factors that affect employees' turnover intention. Some of these are positive and some are negative. For example, workplace stress (Onay and Kilci, 2011), mobbing (Yildiz, 2018) increases employees' turnover intention, while job satisfaction and organizational commitment reduce employees' turnover intention (Yildiz, 2011a). Internal marketing practices in organizations can also help reduce employees' turnover intention.

Physical education teachers are among the dynamics of the schools. Physical education lesson provides students to be more athletic, healthier and more social (MacNamara et al., 2011). Physical education and sports teachers play a major role in the achievements of students. In addition, physical education and sports teachers are very active in extracurricular sports activities (Boccaro, Kanters, Casper and Forrester, 2008). A number of practices that will motivate physical education teachers in such an important position should be implemented by school administrations. School administrations should increase their satisfaction and minimize the possibility of quitting, in order not to lose their teachers to rival schools. Internal marketing practices can help reduce teachers' turnover intentions.

In this article, the effects of internal marketing, which is considered to be an important issue in terms of school efficiency and performance, on physical education and sports teachers' turnover intentions examined.

2. Method

The data used in this study were collected from physical education and sports teachers in Turkey. The questionnaire was prepared on the internet and teachers were reached with electronic communication tools. The purpose of the study was stated and they were asked to participate. The participants were given a week and the number of questionnaires returned after a week was 201.

In this study, two different scales were used to measure the internal marketing and turnover intention. One is the internal marketing scale named IM-11 developed by Yildiz and Kara (2017). This scale consists of 11 items. The other is the 3-item turnover intention scale developed by Landau and Hammer (1986). Scale items were measured on a five-point (1=strongly disagree; 5=strongly agree) Likert type scale.

3. Findings

3.1. Demographic Findings of Teachers

78.6% of the teachers are male, 62.2% are married, 47.3% are 26-35 years old. 87.6% of the teachers have an undergraduate degree. 68.7% of the teachers are permanent and only 12.4% of them have administrative positions. Most teachers (37.8%) have a working period of 1-5 years (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Findings of Teachers

Variables		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	158	78.6
	Female	43	21.4
Age	25 and less	24	11.9
	26-35	95	47.3
	36-45	62	30.8
	46-55	18	9.0
	56 and over	2	1.0
Marital status	Married	125	62.2
	Single	76	37.8
Education	Undergraduate	176	87.6
	Graduate	23	1.4
	Doctorate	2	1.0
Employment status	Permanent status	138	68.7
	Contractual status	63	31.3
Administrative position	No	176	87.6
	Yes	25	12.4
School level served	Middle	118	58.7
	Lycée	83	41.3
Length of working life	1-5 years	76	37.8
	6-10	53	26.4
	11-15	35	17.4
	16-20	15	7.5
	21-25	16	8.0
	26-30	6	3.0

3.2. Reliability Analysis of the Scales

In the reliability analysis, the reliability coefficients of the scales were found to be quite high. The alpha coefficient of the internal marketing scale is 0.951, the turnover intention is 0.818.

3.3. Correlation Analysis

According to Pearson's correlation findings, there is a significant and negative relationship between internal marketing and turnover intention. As the working time increases, teachers' turnover intentions decreases. This indicates that teachers like their professions (Table 2).

Table 2: Correlation Analysis of Variables

Independent variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. Gender	1								
2. Age	-.131	1							
3. Marital status	.194**	-.451**	1						
4. Education	-.190**	.179*	-.200**	1					
5. Employment status	.118	-.558**	.557**	-.130	1				
6. Administrative duty	-.050	.036	.079	.394**	.005	1			
7. School level served	.031	.023	-.112	.105	.000	.021	1		
8. Length of working life	-.079	.802**	-.448**	.124	-.569**	-.017	.006	1	
9. Internal marketing	-.058	.112	.035	.119	-.078	.069	-.047	.030	1
10. Turnover intention	-.017	-.222**	.299**	.012	.341**	.048	.015	-.253**	-.301**

*P<0.01; **P<0.05

3.4. Regression Analysis between Internal Marketing and Turnover Intention

According to the regression analysis, internal marketing affects teachers' turnover intentions significantly and negatively (Table 4). If internal marketing practices are good in schools, teachers may not have turnover intentions.

Table 4: Regression Analysis between Internal Marketing and Turnover Intention

R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	P
.301	.090	.086	19.764	.000
	Standardized beta value		t	
Internal marketing		-.301*	-4.446	.000

Independent variable: Internal marketing; Dependent variable: Turnover intention

*P<0.01

4. Conclusion

Our study has shown that internal marketing can help reduce physical education and sports teachers' turnover intentions. Leaving jobs is a serious problem for organizations. Because, in the case of untimely employees leaving their jobs, there will be a disruption in the service provided by the organizations to the customers. This will cause customer satisfaction to decrease. Decreasing customer satisfaction means decreasing the efficiency of organizations.

In the literature, there are similar studies to our study conducted in various professional fields. In their research on nurses working in hospitals, Ha and Choi (2007) found that internal marketing increased nurses' job satisfaction and decreased their turnover intention. In a similar study on nurses, Lee, Kim and Yoon (2011) found that internal marketing reduced their turnover intentions. Chang and Chang (2008), in their work on tourism and leisure hotel employees, found that internal marketing reduced employees' turnover intentions. The authors stated that within the internal marketing practices, employees will not have turnover intentions if they are provided practices such as the necessary training and development opportunities, rewarding their performance, supporting from managers and participating in the decisions, listening to the problems

of the employees. In a study on employees working sports organizations, Yildiz (2014) found that internal marketing has increased the job satisfaction of the employees and reduced the turnover intention.

When the studies in the field of education are examined, the works of Yuce and Kavak (2017) attract attention. The researchers examined the effect of internal marketing on teachers' turnover intention. At the end of the research, they found that internal marketing decreased the teachers' turnover intentions.

The most important element of internal marketing practices is that senior management shows effective leadership (Wieseke, Ahearne and Lam, 2009). Yildiz (2018) emphasizes that if there is effective leadership in organizations, the problems experienced by the employees will decrease and therefore the quits will decrease. It is also suggested that effective leadership will increase both organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior of employees (Kent and Chelladurai, 2001; Yildiz, 2011b). Another thing that is effective in reducing employees' turnover intention is to improve the quality of working life (Yildiz, 2013). Internal marketing practices increase teachers' quality of work life and increase their organizational commitment (Yu, Yen, Barnes and Huang, 2019; Yuce and Kavak, 2017) and extra role feelings (Abzari and Ghujali, 2011). Thus, teachers can feel more willing to work voluntarily for their students and school. As teachers are the most important dynamics of schools, highly motivated teachers will achieve their educational achievements both on a student and school basis. Thus, the image of the school in front of the parents and society will increase.

About the Author(s)

Muhammed Ömer Eren is a Physical Education and Sports Teacher. He is also a doctoral student in physical education and sports program at Adnan Menderes University, Turkey.

Gökhan Dokuzoğlu is a Physical Education and Sports Teacher. He is also a doctoral student in physical education and sports program at Adnan Menderes University, Turkey.

References

- Abbas, M., Raja, U., Darr, W. and Bouckennooghe, D. (2012). Combined effects of perceived politics and psychological capital on job satisfaction, turnover intentions, and performance. *Journal of Management*, 40(7), 1813-1830.
- Abzari, M. and Ghujali, T. (2011). Examining the impact of internal marketing on organizational citizenship behavior. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 3(4), 95-104.
- Ahmed, P. and Eafiq, M (2003). Internal marketing issues and challenges. *European Journal of Marketing*, 37(9), 117-1186.

- Berry, L. L. (1995). Relationship marketing of services-growing interest, emerging perspectives. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 23(4), 236-245.
- Berry, L. L. and Parasuraman, A. (1991). *Marketing Services*. The Free Press, New York.
- Boccaro, J., Kanters, M. A., Casper, J. and Forrester, S. (2008). School physical education, extracurricular sports, and lifelong active living. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 27(2), 155-166.
- Chang, C-P. and Chang, W-C. (2008). Internal marketing practices and employees' turnover intentions in tourism and leisure hotels. *The Journal of Human Resource and Adult Learning*, 4(2), 161-172.
- Ha, N. S. and Choi, J. (2007). The effects of clinical nurse's internal marketing on job satisfaction, turnover intention, and customer orientation. *Journal of Korean Academy of Nursing Administration*, 13(2), 231-241.
- Kent, A. and Chelladurai, P. (2001). Perceived transformational leadership, organizational commitment, and citizenship behavior: A case study in intercollegiate athletics. *Journal of Sport Management*, 15(2), 135-159.
- Koys, D.J. (2001). The effects of employee satisfaction, organizational citizenship behavior, and turnover on organizational effectiveness: A unit-level, longitudinal study. *Personnel Psychology*, 54(1), 101-114.
- Landau, J. and Hammer, T. H. (1986). Clerical employees' perceptions of intra organizational career opportunities. *Academy of Management Journal*, 29(2), 385-404.
- Lee, H., Kim, M-S. and Yoon, J-A. (2011). Role of internal marketing, organizational commitment, and job stress in discerning the turnover intention of Korean nurses. *Japan Journal of Nursing Science*, 8(1), 87-94.
- MacNamara, A., Collins, D., Bailey, R., Toms, M., Ford, P. and Pearce, G. (2011) Promoting lifelong physical activity and high level performance: Realising an achievable aim for physical education. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 16(3), 265-278.
- Mahdi, A. F., Zin, M. Z. M., Nor, M. R. M., Sakat, A. A. and Naim, A. S. A. (2012). The relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 9(9), 1518-1526.
- Onay, M. and Kilci (2011). The effect of job stress and burnout on turnover intentions: waiters and chefs. *Organizasyon ve Yönetim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 3(2), 363-372.
- Poddar, A. and Madupalli, R. (2012). Problematic customers and turnover intentions of customer service employees. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 26(7), 551-559.
- Rafiq, M. and Ahmed, P. (2000). Advances in the internal marketing concept: definition, synthesis and extension. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 14(6), 449-462.
- Tabancali, E. and Korumaz, M. (2014). Talent management in educational organizations. *International Journal of Social Science*, 25(1), 139-156.
- Wieseke, J., Ahearne, M. and Lam, S. K. (2009). The role of leaders in internal marketing. *Journal of Marketing*, 73(2), 123-145.

- Yildiz, S. M. (2011a). The relationship among internal marketing, job satisfaction and organizational commitment: An investigation of coaches working in sports schools. *Selcuk University Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 13(2), 216-225.
- Yildiz, S. M. (2011b). The relationship between leader member exchange and organizational citizenship behavior in public organizations providing sports services. *Selcuk University Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 13(3), 323-329.
- Yildiz, S. M. (2013). The effect of quality of work life on employee turnover intention in sports and physical activity organizations. *Ege Academic Review*, 13(3), 317-324.
- Yildiz, S. M. (2014). The role of internal marketing on job satisfaction and turnover intention: An empirical investigation of sport and physical activity organizations. *Ege Academic Review*, 14(1), 137-146.
- Yildiz, S. M. and Kara, A. (2017). A unidimensional instrument for measuring internal marketing concept in the higher education sector: IM-11 Scale. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 25(3), 329-342.
- Yildiz, S. M. (2018). An empirical analysis of the leader-member exchange and employee turnover intentions mediated by mobbing: Evidence from sport organizations. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 31(1), 480-497.
- Yu, Q., Yen, D. A., Barnes, B. R. and Huang, Y-A. (2019). Enhancing firm performance through internal market orientation and employee organizational commitment. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 30(6), 964-987.
- Yuce, A. and Kavak, O. (2017). The influence of internal marketing activities on organizational commitment and turnover intention: A research. IV. IBANESS Congress Series – Russe, Bulgaria.

Muhammed Ömer Eren, Gökhan Dokuzođlu
CAN INTERNAL MARKETING HELP TO REDUCE PHYSICAL EDUCATION
AND SPORTS TEACHERS' TURNOVER INTENTION?

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).